

Role of Mathematics and Computer Science Education in Strengthening Early Childhood STEM Learning: A Prerequisite for Innovative National Growth and Development

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Abstract

This paper explores the critical role of early childhood education in Mathematics and Computer Science as foundational pillars for national development. In the 21st century, the global demand for technologically literate and analytically competent citizens underscores the need to begin STEM education at an early stage. The study highlights how cognitive development in young learners can be enhanced through early exposure to problem-solving, logical reasoning, and computational thinking. Drawing upon existing literature, educational theories, and policy frameworks, this paper presents evidence-based arguments for integrating structured Mathematics and Computer Science curricula at the foundational level. It examines the challenges faced in implementing these programs, particularly in developing nations, and proposes strategic solutions involving teacher training, curriculum redesign, and stakeholder collaboration. The paper concludes that effective early childhood Mathematics and Computer Science education not only fosters individual cognitive growth but also catalyzes innovation, economic empowerment, and sustainable national development.

Keywords: Early Childhood, STEM Learning, Mathematics, Computer Science, Innovative National Growth and Development.

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly digital and data-driven world, the importance of early exposure to mathematical and computational concepts is no longer optional but essential for equipping children with the foundational skills necessary for success in the 21st century. Early childhood is a critical period for cognitive and skill development, and educational interventions during this stage have long-term impacts on a child's academic and professional trajectory. Mathematics nurtures logical reasoning, problem-solving abilities, and abstract thinking, while Computer Science introduces children to algorithmic thinking, digital literacy, and creativity in using technology (Anyagh et al 2018, cited in Idehen & Ofuonyebuzor, 2024). The role of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education in this 21st century in driving socio-economic growth and national development cannot be overstated. Among the critical components of STEM, Mathematics and Computer Science have emerged as foundational pillars

that fuel innovation, technological advancement, and problem-solving capabilities across all sectors. Consequently, the need to strengthen early childhood STEM learning in Mathematics and Computer Science has become a central focus for educators, policymakers, and national development strategists alike. The early introduction of STEM-related concepts, particularly Mathematics and Computer Science, not only cultivates cognitive and analytical skills in young learners but also lays the groundwork for a robust future workforce capable of meeting the demands of a technologically-driven global economy (Keysight Technologies (2023)).

This article titled "The Role of Mathematics and Computer Science Education in Strengthening Early Childhood STEM Learning: A Prerequisite for Innovative National Growth and Development" explores the indispensable function that early STEM education plays in nurturing foundational competencies that are vital for national innovation. It emphasizes the importance of exposing children to age-appropriate and engaging STEM experiences that ignite curiosity, foster logical reasoning, and develop computational thinking from an early age. Research has shown that early engagement in Mathematics and Computer Science cultivates a lifelong interest in STEM fields, reduces gender disparities in STEM participation, and enhances children's ability to grasp complex concepts in later educational stages.

Moreover, Keysight Technologies (2023) noted further that in a world increasingly driven by data, algorithms, and automation, nations that prioritize early STEM education are more likely to produce citizens who are not only consumers of technology but also creators and innovators. Such an educational foundation positions young learners to become critical thinkers, problem-solvers, and future leaders in science and technology. Thus, integrating comprehensive and inclusive STEM learning opportunities at the foundational level is not just an educational imperative but a strategic national investment.

According to Wasagu, (2019) National development in the 21st century relies heavily on innovation, technological advancement, and human capital development. For countries, especially those in the Global South, to remain competitive, they must prioritize building a robust educational foundation in STEM—particularly Mathematics and Computer Science—from the early years. He posits that neglecting these core disciplines at the foundational level poses a threat to national growth and global relevance.

Despite their importance, early childhood Mathematics and Computer Science education are often underemphasized in curriculum design, teacher preparation, and education policy. This paper aims to underscore the need for deliberate investments and systemic reforms to integrate these disciplines effectively into early learning systems.

This study critically examines the theoretical foundation for early STEM instruction in Mathematics and Computer Science, evaluates current practices and pedagogical approaches, and proposes actionable strategies for policymakers, curriculum developers, and educators to enhance early childhood STEM education. Ultimately, it argues that a well-structured early STEM education system is a prerequisite for sustainable national development, economic competitiveness, and global relevance in the digital age.

Therefore, this paper will examine the following:

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- Theories on early childhood cognitive development (Piaget, Vygotsky).**
- The significance of early STEM education in international frameworks (UNESCO, UNICEF).**
- Empirical studies linking early Mathematics and Computer Science education with later academic success.**
- Current practices in various countries and the gaps observed in developing nations.**
- The Role of Early Mathematics Education**
- The Role of Early Computer Science Education**
- Challenges in Implementing Early Childhood STEM Education**
- Strategies for Effective Implementation**
- Implications for National Development**
- Conclusion**

Theories on early childhood cognitive development (e.g., Piaget, Vygotsky)

Understanding the theories of cognitive development plays a crucial role in shaping effective strategies for early childhood STEM education, especially in Mathematics and Computer Science. Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, two of the most influential theorists in developmental psychology, provide foundational insights that inform pedagogical approaches aimed at fostering innovative thinking from an early age. Jean Piaget (1952) posits that children move through four distinct stages of cognitive development: sensorimotor, preoperational, concrete operational and formal operational. Each stage represents a new way of thinking and understanding the world. For early childhood STEM education, particularly in Mathematics and Computer Science, Piaget's preoperational stage (ages 2-7) is critical. This is the stage where children begin to use symbols and language to explore ideas but still lack the capacity for logical operations. Effective STEM instruction must therefore use concrete, visual, and hands-on learning experiences. For example, manipulatives, puzzles, coding games, and pattern recognition activities help children internalize foundational mathematical and computational concepts through active exploration. Piaget emphasized the importance of discovery learning—an approach where learners construct knowledge through experiences. Applying this to early STEM education encourages curiosity, problem-solving, and conceptual understanding, thereby laying the cognitive groundwork for future innovation and national development.

Lev Vygotsky's theory complements Piaget's ideas by emphasizing the social and cultural context of learning. Central to his theory is the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)—the gap between what children can do independently and what they can do with guidance and support. Aligning with early STEM education, Vygotsky (1978) highlighted the role of scaffolding by educators, peers, and technology. According to Vygotsky, collaborative

learning, guided instruction, and interactive digital tools are vital for helping young learners grasp abstract concepts in Mathematics and Computer Science. For example, using age-appropriate programming platforms with adult guidance helps children develop computational thinking even before they fully understand formal logic. Vygotsky also underlined the importance of language in cognitive development. He posited that since mathematical and computational thinking rely heavily on symbolic language, introducing relevant vocabulary and encouraging dialogue during STEM activities enhances both cognitive and linguistic developments which are essential for nurturing innovative thinkers.

The application of Piaget's and Vygotsky's theories in early childhood STEM education fosters a generation of learners equipped with critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills. These are the foundational competencies needed in a knowledge-driven economy. By aligning educational practices with developmental readiness and sociocultural support, we cultivate young minds capable of contributing to scientific advancement and technological innovation. Therefore, effective early childhood STEM education in Mathematics and Computer Science is not only pedagogically sound but also a strategic investment in national growth and development. Grounding educational policies and classroom practices in these cognitive theories ensures that learners are prepared to meet the demands of a rapidly changing and innovation-driven world.

The significance of early STEM education in international frameworks (UNESCO and UNICEF)

The global relevance of early childhood STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education—particularly in Mathematics and Computer Science—is firmly rooted in international frameworks championed by organizations such as UNESCO and UNICEF. These institutions recognize the critical role of early STEM engagement in fostering cognitive, social, and technological competencies that are essential for sustainable national development and global competitiveness (Keysight Technologies (2023). UNESCO, (2021) in its Education 2030 Framework for Action, underscores the importance of quality early childhood care and education (ECCE) as the foundation for lifelong learning and human development. The organization advocates for the integration of STEM education at the foundational level, emphasizing that early exposure to Mathematics and Computer Science cultivates analytical thinking, problem-solving abilities, creativity, and digital literacy—all of which are crucial for innovation-driven economies. UNESCO also highlighted that equitable access to early STEM education can help bridge gender and socio-economic gaps, thereby promoting inclusive and equitable quality education (UNESCO & UNICEF, 2024).

Similarly, UNICEF recognized that early learning experiences significantly shape a child's cognitive and emotional development. Through its "Early Moments Matter" campaign and other ECCE initiatives, UNICEF promotes the inclusion of numeracy and digital skills in early childhood curricula. The organization stresses that building foundational skills in STEM disciplines enhances children's readiness for future learning and work, especially in a world increasingly influenced by technology and digital transformation (UNICEF, 2024). Both UNESCO and UNICEF opined that investing in early STEM education yields long-term

economic and social benefits. By nurturing a generation proficient in Mathematics and Computer Science from an early age, nations can cultivate a workforce equipped to drive innovation, scientific advancement, and technological progress. This aligns with the broader goal of achieving inclusive, knowledge-based, and innovation-driven national growth. Haslip & Gullo, (2018) opined that early STEM education should not only focus on content delivery but also adopt pedagogical strategies that are child-centered, exploratory, and play-based. Such approaches align with how young children learn best and ensure that STEM subjects are introduced in ways that are developmentally appropriate and engaging. UNESCO and UNICEF's frameworks affirmed that effective early childhood STEM education in Mathematics and Computer Science is not merely an academic imperative but a strategic investment. It is a foundational pillar for building a resilient, innovative, and economically vibrant nation capable of meeting the demands of the 21st-century knowledge economy.

Empirical studies linking early Mathematics and Computer Science education with later academic success

Empirical research over the last two decades has consistently demonstrated the critical role Mathematics and Computer Science education play in shaping students' long-term academic and career trajectories. Numerous studies affirmed that foundational STEM skills acquired in early childhood have a compounding effect on later success in education, employment, and societal contribution—key factors in innovative national growth and development. One of the most influential longitudinal studies in early childhood education, conducted by Watts, Duncan, Clements, & Sarama, (2018), on the long-run impact of learning Mathematics during preschool, concluded that early Mathematics proficiency is a stronger predictor of later academic achievement than early reading skills or social-emotional behaviors. The study found that children who entered primary school with advanced Math skills performed better not only in Mathematics but also in reading during their later school years. This establishes a firm empirical basis for prioritizing early Math education as a foundational element in STEM preparedness. Another research by Clements and Sarama (2016) also highlights how introducing Computer Science concepts, such as pattern recognition, sequencing, and logical reasoning, in early education foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Their "Building Blocks" curriculum, which integrates Math and Computer Science into preschool classrooms, significantly improved children's cognitive development and readiness for school.

Furthermore, Bers (2018) explored how programming activities using age-appropriate tools like ScratchJr in early childhood increase children's capacity for computational thinking—a skill now widely recognized as essential across all STEM fields. Her studies showed that young children exposed to such environments developed higher levels of sequencing ability, attention span, and collaborative skills, all of which are crucial for success in the modern academic landscape.

The Early Childhood Longitudinal Study (ECLS-K), conducted by the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES), opining to the above, provided robust evidence supporting the long-term benefits of early STEM education. According to the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES), students with early exposure to structured Math and Computer Science

experiences exhibited higher standardized test scores, increased likelihood of pursuing STEM majors in institutions of higher learning, and stronger problem-solving abilities.

Also, studies conducted by the OECD (2020) and UNESCO emphasized that nations investing in equitable and high-quality early STEM education—particularly in Math and Computer Science—tend to experience broader economic and technological advancements. These investments lead to a more skilled workforce, reduced learning gaps, and higher innovation indices, directly linking early education to national development outcomes.

In Nigeria, research by Okafor & Anene (2021) on early childhood education in STEM showed that pilot programs introducing basic coding and Mathematics through play-based learning significantly improved learners' engagement and performance. These findings underscore the importance of integrating culturally-relevant and developmentally-appropriate STEM content into early education to fuel national innovation.

Empirical evidence overwhelmingly supports the notion that effective early childhood education in Mathematics and Computer Science sets a strong foundation for later academic success and national development. By fostering early cognitive skills, improving long-term academic performance, and equipping children with critical 21st-century competencies, early STEM education emerges as a vital strategy for any nation seeking sustainable and innovative growth. Thus, policy-makers, educators, and curriculum developers must prioritize this educational phase to build a future-ready generation.

Current practices in various countries and the gaps observed in developing nations

Globally, there is a growing recognition of the importance of early childhood STEM education, particularly in Mathematics and Computer Science, as a foundational pillar for innovative national growth. However, practices vary significantly between developed and developing nations. For example, in the United States, there is early integration of STEM through national programs like STEM Innovation for Inclusion in Early Education (STEMIE). Digital tools like ScratchJr, Bee-Bots, and tablets are used in classrooms, and they have well-structured teacher training programs in STEM pedagogy. Finland also emphasizes on exploratory, play-based STEM activities starting in preschool. They give equal access to quality education regardless of socio-economic background, and the use of nature and everyday environments to teach mathematical and logical reasoning. In addition, countries like Singapore, South Korea, and United Kingdom integrate STEM, robotics and digital learning in early childhood centers as children are introduced to basic coding and logical thinking through play, and strong culture of academic excellence and early exposure to technology (Karppinen, & Nummenmaa, 2021; Fleer, 2022; Alimisis, 2023; & Kwan & Law, 2024) Heavy investments are made in teacher professional development, with high parental involvement in reinforcing STEM education at home.

Kartimi, Ari, & Dindin (2021) noted that despite the global momentum, developing countries face unique and persistent challenges in early STEM education. Many early childhood education centers lack basic facilities, electricity, or digital tools required for effective STEM instruction. Teachers often lack training in modern STEM pedagogies and are unfamiliar with computer

science principles or hands-on mathematical learning. He took cognizance of the fact that National education policies frequently overlook the importance of early STEM education, focusing instead on literacy and numeracy as STEM is often viewed as too advanced or unnecessary for young children. According to him, there is also the problem of cultural barriers and gender stereotypes. Gender biases discourage girls from engaging with technology and Mathematics from an early age. Government Limited abilities to publicly invest in early childhood STEM has led to over-reliance on donor-funded or NGO-supported projects that are not always sustainable, while minimal context-specific research on the impact of early STEM education in Mathematics and Computer Science, limit evidence-based decision-making.

The Role of Early Mathematics Education

Bers (2018) noted that when children are exposed at pre-school age to early Mathematics, it lays the groundwork for logical reasoning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. These are essential abilities for engaging with STEM disciplines, especially as children progress into more complex areas like computer science and engineering. According to her, exposure to mathematical concepts such as patterns, counting, measurement, and spatial awareness enhances brain development. It supports cognitive growth which is crucial for understanding and applying STEM concepts later in life.

When Mathematics is introduced in a playful, engaging, and age-appropriate way, it stimulates curiosity and a positive attitude toward STEM subjects. This early interest often translates into sustained engagement and pursuit of STEM careers, contributing to a nation's innovative capacity (Okafor & Anene (2021). Mathematics encourages children to explore different strategies for problem-solving. This skill is central to innovation and technology development, which are key drivers of national growth. Many computer science concepts—such as algorithms, sequencing, and logical operations—have their roots in mathematical thinking. A solid foundation in early Mathematics makes it easier for children to grasp programming and computational thinking skills. Quality Mathematics education helps close learning gaps across gender and socio-economic backgrounds. When all children are given a strong mathematical foundation, it increases equitable access to STEM opportunities, which supports inclusive national development. A country that invests in early Mathematics education is effectively investing in its future workforce as skilled, numerate individuals are more capable of contributing to sectors like engineering, technology, finance, and research, which are essential for national development.

The Role of Early Computer Science Education

Computational thinking involves problem-solving processes such as decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, and algorithm design. Introducing young children to basic Computer Science concepts helps them develop logical reasoning and structured thinking from an early age, which also supports mathematical understanding. Early Computer Science activities, such as coding games, robotics, and visual programming tools (like ScratchJr), make learning interactive and fun. These tools can increase children's interest in STEM subjects and foster a positive attitude toward problem-solving and innovation. Computer Science activities can concretize

abstract mathematical ideas. For example, sequencing in coding can reinforce the idea of order and operations in Math. Looping and conditions relate to patterns, logic, and functions. Karppinen, & Nummenmaa, (2021), and Fler, (2022) noted that When children program, they are applying Math in real-world-like scenarios, reinforcing understanding through practice. Computer Science encourages children to design, build, and test their own digital creations. This fosters creative thinking and experimentation, key ingredients for innovation and national development. Agreeing to the above, Alimisis, (2023)and Kwan & Law, (2024) said that early Computer Science education nurtures digital literacy, communication, collaboration, and critical thinking. These skills are essential for children to thrive in a technology-driven economy, ultimately feeding into a more skilled future workforce. Introducing Computer Science early, especially in underserved communities, can promote equity in access to technology and reduce future educational and economic inequalities. Nations that invest in early Computer Science education are preparing a future workforce ready to engage in tech-driven industries, entrepreneurship, and innovation. It creates a pipeline of tech-savvy citizens who can contribute to sectors like AI, data science, robotics, and digital infrastructure.

Challenges in Implementing Early Childhood STEM Education

Implementing early childhood STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education in Nigeria, particularly in Mathematics and Computer Science, is pivotal for fostering innovative national growth and development (Okafor & Anene (2021). However, several challenges hinder its effective execution. Many early childhood education centers in Nigeria lack essential facilities such as safe classrooms, age-appropriate furniture, and learning materials. The absence of well-equipped laboratories and ICT tools limits hands-on experiences crucial for STEM learning. There is a significant deficit of teachers trained specifically in early childhood STEM education. This shortage is more pronounced in rural areas, where attracting and retaining qualified educators is challenging due to low remuneration and limited professional development opportunities. This has led to lack of a standardized, developmentally appropriate STEM curriculum for early learners, leading to inconsistencies in teaching methods and learning outcomes. Frequent policy changes and poor implementation further exacerbate these issues, hindering the establishment of a cohesive educational framework. Limited access to digital technologies and the internet, especially in underserved regions, hampers the integration of computer science into early education. Factors such as high costs, inadequate ICT infrastructure, and lack of digital literacy contribute to this divide. Socioeconomic disparities and cultural perceptions often discourage participation in STEM fields (Chisom, Nnachukwu, & Osawaru, (2024). Gender biases and a lack of awareness about the importance of STEM education can lead to underrepresentation of certain groups, particularly girls, in these areas. Parental involvement is crucial in early childhood education. However, many parents in Nigeria are unaware of the benefits of STEM learning or lack the resources to support their children's education at home. This gap limits reinforcement of STEM concepts outside the classroom. Early childhood STEM programs often suffer from inadequate funding. Dependence on international donors, minimal private sector investment, and inefficient resource utilization impede the development and sustainability of these programs.

Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach involving increased investment in infrastructure, comprehensive teacher training, curriculum development, and community engagement. By overcoming these obstacles, Nigeria can lay a strong foundation for early childhood STEM education, driving innovation and national development.

Strategies for Effective Implementation

Effective implementation of early Mathematics and Computer Science education requires a deliberate, structured, and inclusive approach. It is crucial to develop a robust, age-appropriate, and interdisciplinary curriculum that integrates Mathematics and Computer Science concepts into early childhood education. This should focus on foundational numeracy, logical thinking, basic coding, problem-solving, and pattern recognition. Educators must be equipped with adequate content knowledge and pedagogical skills. Regular training programs, workshops, and certification in early STEM education should be introduced from time to time as this will empower teachers to deliver engaging and impactful lessons (Ezeani, & Obiora-Dimson, 2023).

According to them, incorporating child-friendly technological tools such as tablets, educational apps, coding games, and robotics kits can enhance hands-on learning and stimulate curiosity in young learners. Young children learn best through exploration and play. STEM activities should be fun, interactive, and inquiry-driven to foster creativity, experimentation, and critical thinking. Policies should be in place to ensure that children from all backgrounds—including those in rural and underprivileged communities—have access to quality early STEM education. This includes providing adequate resources and infrastructure. Parents and communities should be engaged in STEM learning as this would help reinforce concepts at home and build a support system around the child’s learning journey. Community-based projects and parental training sessions can be beneficial too.

Implications for National Development

Early Mathematics and Computer Science education has far-reaching implications for national development. Investing in early STEM education lays the foundation for a technologically competent and innovation-driven workforce. Early exposure to logical reasoning and digital literacy prepares children for future careers in science, engineering, and technology. Fostering creativity and critical thinking at a young age cultivates problem-solvers and innovators. This drives entrepreneurship, which is the key to economic diversification and competitiveness. Early interventions help close learning gaps, especially among disadvantaged children, promoting social inclusion and reducing inequality—critical elements for sustainable development. Countries that prioritize STEM education from early childhood are better positioned to lead in knowledge production, technological advancements, and global competitiveness. Early engagement in STEM education, especially among girls, helps challenge stereotypes and supports gender equity in Mathematics and Computer Science careers. A strong foundation in STEM ensures a nation’s ability to develop indigenous technologies, protect its digital infrastructure, and compete in the global tech arena (Keysight Technologies, 2023).

CONCLUSION

Investing in early childhood Mathematics and Computer Science education is not just a pedagogical necessity but a strategic imperative for sustainable national development. Governments, educators, and stakeholders must work collaboratively to design and implement policies and programs that provide young learners with the skills they need to thrive in the digital age.

REFERENCES

- Bers, M. U. (2018). *Coding as a playground: Programming and computational thinking in the early childhood classroom*. Routledge.
- Chisom, O. N., Nnachukwu, C. C., & Osawaru, B. (2024). STEM education advancements in Nigeria: A comprehensive review. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 5(10), 614– 636. <https://fepbl.com/index.php/ijarss/article/view/724>
- Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. (2016). Math, science, and technology in the early grades. *The Future of Children*, 26(2), 75–94. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1118544>
- Ezeani, N. I., & Obiora-Dimson, I. C. (2021, September). Improving STEM learning through digital technology. In *Proceedings of the APWEN 2021 National Conference* (pp. 16–26). Association of Professional Women Engineers of Nigeria. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372535591_IMPROVING_STEM_LEARNING_THROUGH_DIGITAL_TECHNOLOGY
- Fleer, M. (2022). STEM in early childhood education: an international overview of policy and practice. In *The Springer Encyclopedia of Early Childhood Education*. https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-981-16-8679-5_437
- Goos, M., Carreira, S., & Namukasa, I. K. (2023). Mathematics and interdisciplinary STEM education: Recent developments and future directions. *ZDM – Mathematics Education*, 55(7), 1199–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-023-01533-z>
- Haslip, M. J., & Gullo, D. F. (2018). The changing landscape of early childhood education: Implications for policy and practice. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 46, 249-264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-017-0865-7>
- Idehen, F.O, & Ofuonyebuzor, P.A. (2024). Employing Technology Integration to Enhance Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics. *Uniafrica Journal of Education (UJE)*. ISSN: 2971-6004. Volume 3, Issue 2. https://unidel.edu.ng/cms/uploads/publications/unidel_pub_1729356444.pdf
- Karppinen, P., & Nummenmaa, M. (2021). Gamified Coding with Toy Robots in Early Childhood Education: A Finnish Perspective. *Advances in Mobile Learning Educational Research* 1(2) 30–<https://www.syncsci.com/journal/AMLER/article/view/AMLER.2021.02.003>
- Kartimi, K.; Ari S.S.; & Dindin N. (2021). The elementary teacher readiness towards STEM-Based contextual learning in 21st century Era. *Ilkogretimonline-Elementary Education Online*, 2021, 20(1), 145-156.

- Keysight Technologies. (2023, December). The benefits of early STEM education. Keysight Blog. <https://www.keysight.com/blogs/en/keys/exec/2023/12/the-benefits-of-early-stem-education>
- Kwan, T., & Law, Y. (2024). Kindergarten Education Curriculum Guide: Nurturing Holistic Development through Multidisciplinary Learning. *Education Sciences*, 14(4), 357. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/14/4/357>
- OECD. (2020). *Early Learning and Child Well-being: A Study of Five-year-Olds in England, Estonia, and the United States*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/3990407f-en>
- Okafor, C., & Anene, M. (2021). Early childhood education in STEM: Enhancing mathematics and coding skills through play-based learning in Nigeria. *Journal of Early Childhood Education Research*, 9(2), 134–150.
- Piaget, J. (1952). *The origins of intelligence in children* (M. Cook, Trans.). International Universities Press. (Original work published 1936)
- UNESCO. (2021). *STEM and Gender Advancement (SAGA) – A SAGA Toolkit for Policymakers*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374755>
- UNESCO & UNICEF (2024). *Early childhood care and education: The foundation of lifelong learning*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing.
- UNICEF (2020). *Learning through play: Strengthening learning through play in early childhood education programmes*. New York: UNICEF.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes* (M. Cole, V. John-Steiner, S. Scribner, & E. Souberman, Eds. & Trans.). Harvard University Press. (Original works published 1930–1935)
- Wasagu, M.A.(2019). Keynote Address. 60th Annual Conference Proceedings, STAN, 1 – 16.
- Watts, T. W., Duncan, G. J., Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. (2018). What is the long-run impact of learning mathematics during preschool? *Child Development*, 89(2), 539–555. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12713>

